

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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REVOLUTIONIZING ENGLISH EDUCATION: INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO COMMON TEACHING CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, learning foreign languages has become the demand of the time, and students face difficulties during this learning process. This article is devoted to highlighting some problems that arise in the process of teaching and learning foreign languages. At the same time, alternative solutions to these problems are presented.

Keywords: teaching process, teachers, students, English language, teaching resources.

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi kunda chet tillarini o'rganish davr talabiga aylangan va bu o'quv jarayonida o'quvchilar qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishmoqda. Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitish va o'rganish jarayonida yuzaga keladigan ba'zi muammolar to'g'risida so'z boradi.. Shu bilan birga, ushbu muammolarni hal qilishning muqobil usullari taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: dars jarayoni, o'qituvchilar, o'quvchilar, ingliz tili, o'qitish resurslari.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время изучение иностранных языков стало требованием времени, и студенты сталкиваются с трудностями в этом процессе обучения. В данной статье говорится о некоторых проблемах, возникающих в процессе преподавания и изучения иностранных языков. В то же время представлены альтернативные решения этих проблем.

Ключевые слова: учебный процесс, преподаватели, студенты, английский язык, учебные ресурсы.

Today, teaching foreign languages is considered as an urgent issue. Despite the fact that modern methods of teaching English from foreign languages have been

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developed, there are specific problems of mastering. A number of solutions are being developed to overcome these problems.

Some factors affect the quality level of English teaching. They include:

◆ *Limited learning environment*

When it comes to this, it is not about its furniture, but about the fact that students try to communicate in English only during the course of the lesson and the lack of people who constantly communicate in this language around them. As a result, students have difficulties in learning English and communicating in this language. If the students complete the audio and video lessons on the language, they can learn how to pronounce the words and sentences. The fact that students use their mother tongue more than usual in the classroom creates difficulties for them in learning the language. By requiring students to communicate only in English during the lesson, the teacher can achieve progress in their language learning and fluency in pronunciation.

◆ *Constant dominance of students over others*

This situation should not exist at all in the process of teaching English, more precisely, excellent students should continue to actively participate in the lesson, and those with low mastery should not remain so. If they are engaged in extracurricular hours, as a result, they will catch up with their peers in class. It is possible to increase their interest in the lesson by encouraging them more than others and by actively participating in the lesson and giving them the opportunity to express their opinion freely.

◆ *Limited teaching resources*

Even now, there are shortages of teaching resources in some educational institutions. In this matter, many teachers face difficulties during the lesson. That is, teachers do not have enough resources for effective teaching of students. These resources include:

- a. Projectors
- b. Computer systems
- c. Television
- d. CD players.

The process of teaching and learning with them will be very effective and at the same time interesting.

◆ *Limited time*

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Language teaching, which is considered a natural means of both written and oral communication, requires continuity. Time is very important in teaching English. The lesson time allocated for this subject is very little. In addition, the number of students in the class is very large. This requires a lot of energy and time from the teacher. As mentioned above, due to the lack of time, the teacher cannot deal with each student sufficiently. As a result, a student who does not fully understand the subject will be left behind in the lesson. As a solution to this problem, teachers can divide the class into several small groups and achieve the effectiveness of the lesson by conducting separate lessons.

◆ *Conducting lesson in the same order*

In this case, it is assumed that the lesson will be conducted after checking the task and using the exercises in the book, that is, using the old methods. In order to make lessons interesting, teachers are recommended to organize interclass educational competitions, to form healthy competition among students, and to use teaching methods through educational games.

Teachers should not only teach students English or develop their English skills, such as reading, writing, listening and speaking. On the contrary, they should help and encourage them by giving them a passion for English, a good attitude and great motivation.

As there is a solution to every problem, there is a solution to the problems mentioned above. These are:

✚ *Use of multimedia during the lesson*

New, modern devices and gadgets specially designed for education help to improve the teaching and learning of English. Because instead of information written in books, it is easier for students to understand ideas through visual images, videos, and audios.

✚ *Manage lesson and timetable rules*

Strict rules and schedules should be made for classes. Discipline and rules are important in the process of learning English. Students must follow these rules, come to class on time, complete assignments on time, and not use mobile phones in the auditorium. If the students violate any of these rules, it is necessary to inform their parents.

✚ *Organization of educational competitions in classes*

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Competition plays an important role in learning English, especially in developing speaking skills. Examples include debates and quizzes. These competitions not only help students improve their language skills, but also increase their self-confidence and form teamwork skills.

In conclusion, the problems arising in the process of teaching a foreign language considered in the article lie in the lack of necessary educational resources, the fact that old teaching methods are still used in most educational institutions, and the educational environment is not good. It is possible to increase the level of students' mastery of the lessons and achieve the effectiveness of the lesson through the teaching methods presented above as a solution to these problems.

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